

Wedding Gown Making with Sasirangan Fabric and Borneo's Motif Embroidery

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Abstract: Indonesia has a great culture, including its traditional fabrics. This traditional fabric needs to be preserved, so it does not extinct. One of the efforts to preserve traditional fabrics is to use these traditional fabrics and introduce them to the community. Sasirangan is one of the traditional fabrics of the Banjar tribe from South Borneo. This fabric is made using a tie dye technique that produces a variety of motifs that are special or unique from its region. This sasirangan fabric was originally a cloth used by nobles, to attend traditional ceremonies. However, traditional ceremonies were rarely carried out. This can make the traditional fabric become extinct. One way to introduce this sasirangan fabric to the public is to make a wedding gown using sasirangan fabric. Sasirangan is used on body parts and ribbon-shaped applications on the back of part the dress. In addition, on this wedding gown, embroidery application is added with a regional motif from Borneo, mangosteen motif and jaruju leaves on the chest and back, and the embroidery is also added to the skirt of the wedding gown.

Keywords: Sasirangan; Banjar tribe; Borneo; Traditional fabric; Wedding gown

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1. Introduction

Indonesia is a country with a various culture. Sasirangan fabric is one of the Indonesian cultural, a traditional fabric from Banjar tribe, South Borneo. The uniqueness of this fabric can be seen in the variety of its motifs. Sasirangan comes from the word "sirang" (local language) which means tied or sewn by hand and drawn by the thread [10]. In the very beginning, sasirangan fabric was used as traditional clothing, usually in the form of headbands, belts for men as well as scarves, veils, or "kemben" for women. This sasirangan fabric was originally only used in traditional ceremonies. Nowadays, traditional ceremonies have rarely been performed. This can cause sasirangan fabric to become extinct. One of the ways that can be done to preserve this sasirangan fabric from the extinction is by introducing the fabric to the community. One of the ways to introduce sasirangan fabric is using the fabric as a wedding gown. Besides using sasirangan fabric, the wedding gown will also be added the embroidery application using Tapuk Manggis (mangosteen pockmark) motif which is a typical motif from Borneo. The examples of Sasirangan fabrics and its motifs are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. (a) The examples of Sasirangan fabrics, (b) Examples of Motifs of Sasirangan Fabrics, 1. Gigi Haruan, 2. KambangKacang, 3. HirisGagatas, 4. Kambang Sasaki, 5. DaunJaruju, 6. Tampuk Manggis, 7. Bintang, 8. KangkungKaubakan, 9. OmbakSinampurkarang, 10. Bayam Raja, 11. KulatKarikit, 12. HirisPudak, 13. UlarPadi, 14. MayangMurai, 15. Naga Balimbur, 16. RamakSahangThe purpose of making a wedding gown using sasirangan fabric is to introduce sasirangan fabric to the public. The goal is to create alternative modern wedding gown using traditional fabrics and preserving Indonesian culture from extinction.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Material

2.1.1 Sasirangan fabric

The motif of sasirangan fabric that be used in this wedding gown is “Tapuk Manggis” (mangosteen pockmark, no. 6 on Fig 1b). The motif comes from flowers on the top of the mangosteen fruit. Each mangosteen has flowers that can estimate the contents of the fruit hidden inside. It has a philosophy of the honesty (five or six mangosteen flowers represent five or six fruit inside). Another motif used in this wedding gown is “DaunJaruju” (jaruju leaves, no 5 on Fig 1b). The philosophy of jaruju leaves is prevent disaster.

2.1.2 Another material

Another material used for wedding gown as shown on Fig.2

Figure 2. Material Used for Wedding Gown

Table 1. Material used for wedding gown

No	Item	Qty
1	Sasirangan fabric	2 plies
2	Sateen fabric	11 m
3	Siffon fabric	11 m
4	Tulle fabric	2 m
5	Organza fabric	2 m
6	Hard tulle fabric	20 m
7	Asahi fabric	2 m
8	Rubber (4 cm width)	1 m
9	Sewing thread	3 cones
10	Swarovsky beads	3 gross
11	Pearl beads 4mm	2 strand
12	Pearl beads 6mm	2 strand
13	Pearl beads 8mm	2 strand
14	Long beads	1 box
15	Lace	11 m
16	Covered button	20 pcs

2.2 Methods

Making wedding gown is starting from making the moodboard (Fig. 3) as the source of inspiration. Then preparing the material, measure the body parts (Table. 2), pattern making (Fig. 4), sewing, fitting the gown and finishing (attaching the application).

Figure 3. Moodboard

Table 2. Body Measurement

No	Item to be measured	Size (cm)
1	Chest girth	90
2	Waist girth	72
3	Neck girth	36
4	Body length	33
5	Chest width	34
6	Shoulder width	12.5
7	Back width	35
8	Back length	37
9	Sleeve length	55
10	Armscye girth	44
11	Highest sleeve point length	13
12	Upper-arm girth	34
13	Wrist girth	19
14	Waist height	85
15	Skirt githr	10 m

Figure 4. Pattern of wedding gown

3. Results

The result of wedding gown can be seen on Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Wedding gown

4. Discussion

The wedding gown made from Sasirangan fabric and the application of the mangosteen embroidery motif has a ballgown silhouette, or L silhouette with a cathedral tail length. The embroidery motif of the mangosteen are spread along the skirt and the tail of the gown. Sasirangan fabric is used in the body of the gown and the ribbon application in the back side of the gown.

The line applied to this bridal is a straight line and curved lines. Straight lines impress tension, certainty, stiffness, and firmness. Curved lines are flexible, beautiful, feminine and soft. Both lines are applied to this bridal dress. Straight lines are found in the pieces, folds, and effects seen from the bridal dress body. While the curved line is more dominant in the embroidery motif made.

The accent that emerges from the clothing details in the form of sasirangan fabric is used on the body parts and the embroidery application arrangement which is placed on the parts that focus on the application of the embroidery technique. Small embroidery applications are placed on the chest and spread in parts of the skirt made in large quantities, while medium and large embroidery applications are made in large quantities but only spread on the skirt. This is intended so that the rhythms generated from the placement of embroidery applications can be seen and become the main focus of this outfit.

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